

A Study of Histomorphology and Staging of Neuroendocrine Neoplasms of the Digestive Tract in a Tertiary Care Center in MaharashtraShriya Patil¹, Yugandhar Patil², Supriya V Patil³, Vijaykumar S Patil⁴¹Assistant professor, Department of Pathology, Prakash institute of medical sciences and research, Islampur, Maharashtra.²Assistant Professor, Department of Radiology, Prakash institute of medical sciences and research, Islampur, Maharashtra³Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Krishna institute of medical sciences, Karad, Maharashtra.⁴Professor, Department of Community medicine, Prakash institute of medical sciences and research, Islampur, Maharashtra

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Neuroendocrine neoplasms/tumors (NETs) of digestive system represent 2% of all GI tumors. It has been seen that incidence of NETs are steadily increasing. Neuroendocrine neoplasms can be challenging to diagnose.**Objectives:** were to study the histopathological features neuroendocrine neoplasms of the digestive tract and to classify them according to histomorphological subtypes and staging as per WHO criteria and TNM staging.**Materials and Methods:** This was a cross-sectional study on 31 cases of primary NETs of digestive tract, which were diagnosed and operated between 2008 to 2017. All slides were diagnosed by two senior histopathologists. Staging was done using WHO 2010 criteria and TNM staging as per American joint cancer committee criteria.**Results:** The most common age of presentation of patients with neuroendocrine neoplasms of digestive system was between 41-60 years, mean age being 53.12 years. The commonest location of digestive system neuroendocrine neoplasms was colon and rectum (19.3%), followed by stomach (13%), appendix (13%) and ampullary region (13%). Most of the cases presented with polypoidal growth (38.9%). On microscopic examination the most frequent pattern of cellular arrangement was of nests of tumor cells (48.38%). The cell showed characteristic monomorphic nuclei with stippled chromatin and granular eosinophilic cytoplasm Invasion into muscularis propria was noted in 66.6% cases. Perineural invasion was observed in more cases (91.3%) compared to lymphovascular invasion (73.9%). Majority (64.5%) of patients had Grade III tumour. Most common tumor type was NEC (39%), followed by NET (35%) and MANEC (26%).**Conclusion:** Colon and rectum followed by stomach are the most common site for neuroendocrine neoplasms of digestive system. Majority of the neoplasms were of grade 1 according to WHO 2010 classification.**Keywords:** Neuroendocrine tumours, digestive system, histomorphology, TNM staging.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction:**

Neuroendocrine neoplasms/tumors (NETs) of digestive system are epithelial neoplasm with neuroendocrine differentiation and originate from diffuse endocrine system located in the gastrointestinal (GI) tract, pancreas, and hepatobiliary system. They represent 2% of all GI tumors. It has been seen that incidence of NETs are steadily increasing. Neuroendocrine neoplasms can be challenging to diagnose. This is a heterogeneous group of tumors which present with variety of clinical symptoms. They can be functional or non-functional. Certain neuroendocrine neoplasm can produce nonspecific symptoms (such as diarrhea,

abdominal pain, flushing, and hypoglycemia) that can be mistaken for other conditions and impede diagnosis. The estimated time for diagnosis of certain types of neuroendocrine neoplasms is up to 5 to 7 years from symptom onset. [1] This delay means that disease may be advanced by the time a neuroendocrine tumor (NET) is diagnosed. In fact, up to half of all neuroendocrine neoplasms patients with histologically defined disease have either regional or distant metastases at diagnosis. Patients with well-differentiated Grade 1/Grade 2 NETs with distant metastases have a median survival of 33 months. Median 5-year survival probability for these

patients is only 35%. [2] It is important to study the clinical and pathologic details of these tumors to better understand the variations with respect to location, grading, and behaviour. However, there are very few dedicated studies on the occurrence and grading of these tumors. Their behaviour is better in comparison to GI conventional adenocarcinoma. [3] In the present study we have tried to compile the histopathological profile of the NETs which were diagnosed on biopsy or resection according to WHO 2010 criteria. [4] The objectives were to study the histopathological features in minimum 30 cases of neuroendocrine neoplasms of the digestive tract received in surgical pathology section of pathology department, and to classify them according to histomorphological subtypes. To do pathological staging as per guidelines of World Health Organization (WHO) Criteria as well as TNM staging according to site as given by American Joint Committee of Cancer.

Material and Methods

This was a cross-sectional study of 31 cases of primary NETs of digestive tract, which were diagnosed and operated between 2008 to 2017 in a tertiary medical center in Maharashtra. The available data for all the patients as regards with age, location of tumour and stage was collected. Data regarding distant and regional metastasis was inadequate for analysis and hence not included in the study. All the data used in the present study was obtained from the records of histopathology section of the department of pathology. Inclusion Criteria: All diagnosed cases of neuroendocrine neoplasms of digestive system. The availability of properly preserved sample blocks was an important inclusion criterion. Exclusion Criteria: Cases in which records/ slides/ blocks were not available were not included in the present study. Tissue collection: The tissues of the test population received were evaluated by histopathological processing and examination (HPE).

All the slides were evaluated by two senior histopathologists. Tissue processing: Tissues were fixed in 10% formal saline overnight, for an average period of 18 hrs. Adequate fixation ensured. The tissue was grossed. The location, size and color of the tumors were examined in all resected specimens. Representative sections were taken, and blocks processed in the Leica tissue processor Leica TP 1020 with a cycle of 24 hours, after which the processed tissue was embedded into wax blocks. The wax blocks were trimmed using the Leica rotary microtome Leica RM 2125 RT. Sections were taken onto slides and stained by the routine Haematoxylin and eosin (H&E) stain. The H & E sections were reviewed and histomorphological feature including cellular arrangement, cell morphology, invasion into muscle wall, perineural and vascular invasion pertaining to various sites were analysed in all cases. The diagnosis of neuroendocrine tumor was made

on both biopsies as well as resected specimens. The classification and grading of these tumors were done according to WHO 2010 classification. [3] Classification of Neuroendocrine neoplasms of digestive system: Neuroendocrine neoplasms of digestive system were classified according to WHO 2010 classification. 1. NET G1 (Carcinoid), 2. NET G2, 3. NEC (Large cell/Small cell type), 4. Mixed Adenoneuroendocrine Ca (MANEC), 5. Hyperplastic and Preneoplastic lesion. The data are analysed and presented in table as percentages.

Results

There were 31 cases of NET diagnosed in the study period which included 17 male and 14 female patients. The diagnosis was made on biopsies in 13 cases and resected surgical specimens were available in 18 patients. Table 1 shows the distribution of cases based on characteristics age, location, size of tumour, and gross features. The age of patients ranged from 18 to 82 years, with a mean of 53.12 years. The highest numbers of cases were seen in the age group of 41-60 years (42%).

Neuroendocrine neoplasms were identified in GI tract of 23 patients, whereas 2 were identified in pancreas and 6 were in hepatobiliary system. There were 2 multicentric cases. One was involving small intestine presented with 6 strictures and had multiple polypoid lesions. Other case was presented with multiple polypoid lesions involving appendix, ileocaecal junction and caecum. Commonest location of digestive system neuroendocrine neoplasms was colon and rectum region (n=6, 19.3%), followed by stomach (n=4, 13%), appendix (n=4, 13%) and ampullary region (n=4, 13%).

Gross features were studied in 18 resected specimens. Maximum number of the tumors were less than 4cm in size (maximum dimension) (n=10/18; 55.5%). Only one case was having tumor size of 9cm. About 7 out of 18 (38.9%) cases had polypoid growth. 5/18 (27%) cases were having ulceroproliferative growth and 4/18 (22.3%) cases had nodular growth. Only one case was showing cystic lesion in head of pancreas and one case was with thickened appendiceal wall.

Table 2 shows the microscopic features and grading of the NETS in the study. The most frequent pattern of cellular arrangement was of nests of tumor cells (n=15/31; 48.38%). The next most frequent pattern was that of trabeculae and sheets (n=10/31; 32.25%). Majority of cases from colon and rectum showed small nests of tumor cells as predominant pattern (n=6/31; 19.35%). Islands and trabecular pattern were the most frequently observed in appendix and small intestine (n=4/31; 12.9% and n=7/31; 22.58% respectively). Tumor cells showed characteristic monomorphic nuclei with stippled chromatin and granular eosinophilic cytoplasm. Out of the 21 cases studied, invasion into muscle wall was noted

in 14 (66.6%) cases. Perineural and lymphovascular invasion was observed in 18 resected specimens in addition to that it was also noted in 5 biopsy specimens. Out of 23 cases studied, perineural invasion was present in 21 (91.3%) cases.

Perineural invasion (21/31; 91.3%) was observed in more cases compared to lymphovascular invasion (17/31; 73.9%). Picture 1 and Picture 2 show microscopic findings of NETs in our study. The grading was done according to WHO 2010 criteria. It included 6 cases (19.4%) of grade I, 5 cases (16.1%) of grade II and 20 cases (64.5%) of grade III. Table 3 shows the grading based on location of

neuroendocrine tumours and table 4 show TNM staging of cases in the study. About 75% of stomach neoplasms were G3 and 25% were G1. 40% of small intestinal neoplasms were of G1, 40% of were MANEC and 20% were of G3.

In appendix 75% tumor were of G2 and 25% were of grade 1. In colon and rectum 50% neoplasms were of MANEC, 33% were of G2 and 17% were of G1. In liver 80% of neuroendocrine neoplasms were of G3 and 20% were MANEC. In Pancreas one case was of G1 and one was of G3. In esophagus only one case reported, and it was of G3. In gall bladder one case of MANEC was reported.

Table 1: Descriptive characteristics of study participants (N=31)

Variable	Number (n)	%	Variable	Number(n)	%
Age in years	n	%	Location	n	%
0-20	1	3	Oesophagus	1	3.2
21-40	6	20	Stomach	4	13
41-60	13	42	Ampullary region	4	13
61-80	10	32	Small Intestine	3	9.6
>80	1	3	Appendix	4	13
Size of tumor (in cms)	n	%	Colon & Rectum	6	19.3
0-4	10	55.5	Anal Canal	0	0
4.1-8	7	39	Liver and intrahepatic biliary duct	5	16.1
>8	1	5.5	Gall bladder & Extrahepatic biliary duct	1	3.2
Gross features	n	%	Pancreas	2	6.4
Polypoidal growth	7	38.9	Multicentric (Involving ileocaecal junction, caecum, appendix)	1	3.2
Nodular growth	4	22.3			
Ulceroproliferative growth	5	27.8			
Thickened wall	1	5.5			
Cystic lesion	1	5.5			

Table 2: Microscopic features and grading of neuroendocrine tumours in the study

Variable	Number (n)	Feature	Variable	Number (n)	%
Location (n=30)	n	Histopathological Pattern	Invasion into muscularis propria (n=21)	n	%
Oesophagus	1	Sheets	Present	14	66.6
Stomach	4	Nests, sheets, glands	Absent	7	33.4
Small intestine	5	Nests, glands, trabeculae, islands	Perineural invasion	N	%
Ampulla	2	Islands, trabeculae, sheets	Present	21	91.3
Appendix	4	Islands, trabeculae	Absent	2	8.7
Colon & Rectum	6	Nests, sheets, islands, glands	Lymphovascular invasion (n=23)	n	%
Liver and intrahepatic Biliary duct	5	Nests, sheets, glands	Present	17	73.9
Gall bladder and Extrahepatic Biliary duct	1	Islands	Absent	6	26.1
Pancreas	2	Nests, islands, trabeculae, pseudoglandular	Type of neoplasm (n=31)	n	%
Grade (WHO 2010 criteria) (n=31)	n	%	NET	11	35

I	6	19.4	NEC	12	39
II	5	16.1	MANEC	8	26
III	20	64.5			

Table 3. Grading according to location of neuroendocrine tumours in the study

Location	Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3	MANEC
Oesophagus	-	-	1(100%)	-
Stomach	1(25%)	-	3(75%)	-
Small intestine	2(40%)	-	1(20%)	2(40%)
Ampulla	-	-	1(50%)	1(50%)
Appendix	1(25%)	3(75%)	-	-
Colon and rectum	-	2(33%)	1(17%)	3(50%)
Anal Canal	-	-	-	-
Liver and IHBD	-	-	4(80%)	1(20%)
Gall bladder and EHBD	-	-	-	1(100%)
Pancreas	1(50%)	-	1(50%)	-

Table 4: Distribution based on TNM staging

Variable	Number (n)	%	Variable	Number (n)	%
Location	Number of cases	TNM Grading (Stage)	Location	Number of cases	TNM Grading (Stage)
1. Oesophagus	1	T2N1Mx (Stage IIB)	4. Ampulla	1	T1N0Mx (Stage IA)
	1	T3NxMx (stage IIB)		1	T3N0Mx (Stage IIA)
2. Stomach	1	T2NxMx (Stage IIA)	5. Appendix	2	T1NxMx (Stage I)
	1	T3N1Mx (Stage IIIB)		2	T1NoMx (Stage I)
3. Small Intestine	1	T4N1Mx (Stage IIIB)	6. Colon and rectum	1	T3N0Mx (Stage IIB)
	1	T3N1Mx (Stage IIIB)		2	T3N1Mx (Stage IIIB)
	1	T1N0Mx (Stage I)	7. Pancreas	1	T2N0Mx (Stage IB)

Figure 1: Photomicrograph showing nest of tumor cells in neuroendocrine neoplasm. (H&E,100x)

Figure 2: Photomicrograph showing tumor cells having monomorphic nuclei with stippled chromatin and granular eosinophilic cytoplasm. (H&E,100x)

Discussion

The nomenclature and classification of neuroendocrine neoplasms has undergone significant change in last few years. The neuroendocrine neoplasms of digestive system are rare accounting for 2.5 to 5 cases per 100000. [5] In the present study, most common age group affected was 41- 60 years. 42% of cases were recorded in this age group. Like our study, there was an article published by M Uppin et al, the where the age ranged from 24-80 years, with maximum number of cases noted in the age group of more than 40 years. [6] In a study done by Maggard et al., and Modlin et al., average age at diagnosis for neuroendocrine neoplasm was 60.9 years and 61.4 years respectively. While in our study the average age for neuroendocrine neoplasms at diagnosis were 53.12 years. [5,7] Similar to our study in a study done by Jin-Hu Fan et al., where the patient's age range was 8-89 years, median age of presentation was 53.0 years and peak age group at the time of diagnosis was 51-60 years. [8]

Joo Young Kim et al., observed distribution patterns of neuroendocrine neoplasms in digestive system seem to be different between eastern and western population. The rectum (48%) was most frequent site of neuroendocrine neoplasms in GI tract of patients in Korea followed by stomach (15%) which was same as our study. [9] A study by M Uppin et al., noted that the commonest location for neuroendocrine neoplasm of GI tract in the study was duodenum and periampullary region (22.5%), followed by stomach (17.5%).

Small intestine was site for neoplasm in 9.6% cases and Ampullary area in 13% cases. [6] Bruna Estrozi et al., observed in their study, which included 773 cases, that most common location for neuroendocrine neoplasm of gastroenteropancreatic tract was stomach (24.5%), followed by small intestine (20.8%). While in our study stomach was involved in 13% cases. In their study, all cases involving appendix were of grade 1, while in our study 75% were grade 2 and 25% were grade 1. [10] In another study done by Meng Zhang et al. they observed the most common location for neuroendocrine neoplasms of digestive system was stomach (24.3%) followed by rectum (24.1%). [11]

A study done by Ting-Ting Li et al., observed that 70-80% of neuroendocrine neoplasms of digestive system were having size 1-2cm, while in our study 55.5% cases were having size of <4cm. Similar to our study most of the cases had polypoidal growth (75- 86%). [12] A study done by Kenichi Hirabayashi et al., observed that NETs were whitish to yellowish or grayish solid tumors with nodular or polypoidal appearance. In contrast NECs showed larger ulcerated masses. In our study 5 cases showed (27.8%) ulceroproliferative growth out of which 3

were MANEC and 2 were NECs. [13] Joo Young Kim et al., reported that jejunal and ileal neuroendocrine neoplasms presented as multiple tumors in one third of the cases. In our study there was one case involving ileum & jejunum, having multiple polypoidal masses with average diameter of 4.5cm. They also had 6 strictures. [9]

A study done by M Uppin et al., they observed that islands and lobules were the most frequent pattern (57.5%) while in contrast to our findings they observed trabeculae and sheets were infrequent pattern (22.5% and 12.5% respectively). Like our study, Kenichi Hirabayashi et al., observed in their study that tumor cell nests in neuroendocrine neoplasms of GI tract were arranged in trabecular or sheet like pattern. They also observed that tumor cells possessed round or oval nuclei with salt and pepper chromatin and granular eosinophilic cytoplasm. [13] M Uppin et al., they observed perineural invasion in 28.5% cases and lymphovascular invasion in 39.2%. Lymphovascular invasion was more frequent than perineural invasion. [6] Jin-Hu Fan et al., observed in their study that 13.8% cases showed vascular invasion and 5.2% cases showed perineural invasion. Vascular invasion (13.8) was more frequent than perineural invasion (5.2%). [8]

Bruna Estrozi studied 773 gastroenteropancreatic neuroendocrine tumors out of which 566(73.2%) were of grade 1, 81(10.5%) were of grade 2 and 126(16.3%) were of grade 3. They also observed that all appendiceal neuroendocrine neoplasms were of grade 1 and 92.1% of esophageal neuroendocrine neoplasms were of grade 3, while in our study 75% of appendiceal neuroendocrine neoplasms were of grade 2 and 25% were of grade 1. There was only one case of esophageal neuroendocrine neoplasm in our study, and it was of grade 3 i.e., neuroendocrine carcinoma. [10] In conclusion, Colon and rectum followed by stomach were the most common site for neuroendocrine neoplasms of digestive system. Majority of the neoplasms were of grade 1 according to WHO 2010 classification.

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